

APPENDIX E – DEVELOPER AND END USERS EVALUATION FORMS

DEVELOPERS

Developer Usability

* Indicates a required question

How easy was it to learn the API documentation? *

1 2 3 4 5

What initial difficulties did you have in remembering the steps? *

Your answer

Did you feel frustrated at any point? *

- Yes
- No

How did you feel when you finished the tasks? *

Your answer

Would you use this API again in other projects? *

- Yes
- No

Would you recommend this API to other developers? *

- Yes
- No

END USERS

Do you believe that this solution contributes to the transparency and traceability of public processes? *

- I totally agree
- Partially agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially disagree

- Totally disagree

Would you use this solution to consult public proceedings? *

- I would definitely use this solution
- I would probably use this solution
- I am unsure whether I would use this solution
- I would probably not use this solution
- I would definitely not use this solution

Would you recommend this solution to other colleagues who use the SEI platform?

- I would definitely recommend this solution to other colleagues
- I would probably recommend this solution to other colleagues
- I am unsure whether I would recommend this solution to other colleagues
- I would probably not recommend this solution to other colleagues
- I would definitely not recommend this solution to other colleagues

What did you find positive about the solution presented? * Your answer

What suggestions for improvement would you make for the solution presented?

Your response

What would be your suggestions for improvement to the solution presented?

Your response